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Aboveground Biomass and Carbon Stock in Urban Trees from Miami Dade County, South Florida.

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Manuscripts should be addressed to:

Dr. Antonio Mijail Perez
Editor
Gaia Learning
9860 SW 32nd ST
Miami, FL 33165
E-mail: mijail64@gmail.com /
gaia.learning21@gmail.com

**Aboveground Biomass and Carbon Stock in Urban Trees from Miami Dade County,
South Florida.**

Antonio Mijail Perez

St. Thomas University

College of Health Sciences and Technology

(C) 786.486.5337, AntonioPerez@stu.edu, 2) (O) 305.628.6603.

Key words

Biomass, carbon capture, Street Trees, South Florida

Abstract

Photosynthesis is the process through which plants and some other organisms convert light energy from the Sun into chemical energy that will be used to fuel the organisms' activities. Biomass is a measure of biological matter, customarily expressed in weight. A quantitative approach was taken to analyze Biomass as a product of Photosynthesis. The project was conducted in the cities of Miami and Doral, Florida, U.S.A., as a part of the General Biology course taught at the Miami Dade College. Perimeters were measured on tree species using a Tailor's Tape as a first step to determining their biomass. This and other procedures could be easily replicated due to their simplicity. We chose the following urban widespread species to be included in the paper based on data quality and considering they may be found in many other locations. Gumbo Limbo, Flamboyant, Mango, Avocado and Yellow Trumpet Tree. Aboveground biomass was calculated using the following formula, $\text{Biomass (Kg/tree)} = 21.297 - 6.953 (\text{DBH}) + 0.74(\text{DBH})^2$, where DBH= Diameter at Breast Height. Students were provided with the Excel spreadsheet containing the formulas already programmed for conducting the calculations in order to facilitate the process. Biomass ranged from 7.28 kg in Yellow Trumpet trees to 18,826.51 kg in Mango trees. Differences observed among species were not significant ($F= 2.52, p > 0.05$).

Palabras claves

Biomasa, captura de carbono, Árboles de la calle, Sur de la Florida

Resumen

La fotosíntesis es el proceso a través del cual las plantas y algunos otros organismos convierten la energía luminosa del Sol en energía química que se utilizará para impulsar las actividades de los organismos. La biomasa es una medida de materia biológica, habitualmente expresada en peso. Se tomó un enfoque cuantitativo para analizar la Biomasa como producto de la Fotosíntesis. El proyecto se llevó a cabo en las ciudades de Miami y Doral, Florida, EE. UU., como parte del curso de Biología General que se imparte en el Miami Dade College. Se midieron los perímetros de las especies arbóreas utilizando una cinta de sastre como primer paso para determinar su biomasa. Este y otros procedimientos podrían replicarse fácilmente debido a su simplicidad. Elegimos las siguientes especies de distribución urbana para incluirlas en el documento en función de la calidad de los datos y considerando que se pueden encontrar en muchos otros lugares. Gumbo Limbo, Flamboyant, Mango, Aguacate y Trompeta Amarilla. La biomasa aérea se calculó utilizando la siguiente fórmula, Biomasa (Kg/árbol) = $21,297 - 6,953 (DAP) + 0,74 (DAP)^2$, donde DAP= Diámetro a la Altura del Pecho. Para facilitar el proceso, se proporcionó a los estudiantes la hoja de cálculo de Excel que contiene las fórmulas ya programadas para realizar los cálculos. La biomasa varió de 7,28 kg en árboles de trompeta amarilla a 18.826,51 kg en árboles de mango. Las diferencias observadas entre especies no fueron significativas ($F= 2.52, p> 0.05$).

Introduction

Photosynthesis is the process that plants and some other organisms use in order to convert light energy from the Sun into chemical energy that will be used to fuel the organisms' activities. Photosynthesis makes life on Earth possible. The input is carbon dioxide, water, and light, and the output is carbohydrates and oxygen (Krogh, 2011). In other words, photosynthesis creates Biomass.

Biomass is a measure of biological matter, customarily expressed in weight. The biomass of a forest is a complex topic that includes all organisms, trees, fungi, insects, and so forth, and is beyond the scope of this book. Tree biomass may be that of a single individual or all individuals occupying a unit of area. Since trees have a substantial moisture content, weights may be either with (i.e., green) or without (i.e., oven-dry) moisture. The biomass of trees is often subdivided into above- and below-ground components with further subdivisions of each. For example, above-ground biomass includes foliage, branches, stem, and bark (Briggs, 1994).

It is important to point out that the increase of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere has resulted in global warming (Krogh, 2011), and a way to prevent Global Warming would be to prevent deforestation and to plant trees in cities and natural areas. Deforestation has caused a decrease in photosynthesis and a detrimental effect on earth.

The project was conducted in the cities of Miami and Doral, Florida, U.S.A., as a part of the General Biology course taught at the Miami Dade College with the purpose of calculating the amount of Biomass produced by local trees. Perimeters were measured using a Tailor's Tape on tree species as a first step to determining their biomass. This and other procedures could be easily replicated due to their simplicity.

Materials and Methods

Measurements: A quantitative approach was taken to analyze Biomass as a product to Photosynthesis. Perimeters are measured on local- widespread tree species as a first step to determining their biomass, as it is shown in the picture below (Fig. 1, 2). Throughout the years and as part of the General Biology Course, at the Miami Dade College, in Miami, we have been calculating the biomass of some tree species and the amount of CO₂ they contain.

Figure 1.-
Measurement of perimeters on trees.

Figure 2.-
Measurement of perimeters on trees.

Perimeters were measured using a Tailor's Tape on tree species as a first step to determining their biomass. Measurements have to be made in centimeters. Perimeters are then transformed into Diameters, and with Diameters the formula below is used to calculate biomass

according to Brown & Iverson (1992). Students were provided with a Excel spreadsheet containing the formulas already programmed for conducting the calculations in order to facilitate the process.

Analysis of Biomass: Perimeters are then transformed into Diameters, and with Diameters the formula below is used to calculate biomass according to Brown & Iverson (1992)

$P = \pi \text{ DBH}$ (Diameter at Breast Height, 130 cm), then:

$$\text{DBH} = P / \pi$$

Once we have Diameters, Biomass may be computed using Brown & Iverson (1992) formula which we programmed into Excel for practical reasons. Formula is as follows (Brown & Iverson, 1992, Segura, 2005):

$$\text{Biomass (Kg/tree)} = 21.297 - 6.953 (\text{DBH}) + 0.74(\text{DBH})^2$$

Results are given in Kg/Tree. In addition, the carbon dioxide stored in plants that according to IPCC is approximately half of the biomass calculated was calculated (IPCC, 1996). In order to calculate Carbon stored in plants we use the following formula:

Carbon stock: The aboveground biomass carbon stock was calculated by assuming that the carbon content is 50% of the total aboveground biomass (Brown & Lugo 1982, Cannel *et al.* 1995, Dixon, 1994, Ravindranath *et al.* 1997, Richter *et al.* 1995, Schroeder 1992).

$$\text{CO}_2 = \text{Biomass} \times 0.5$$

Sampling Sites: The Project was conducted in various neighborhoods from the cities of Miami and Doral, Florida, U.S., as a part of the General Biology course taught at the Miami Dade College, Florida, U.S.

Statistical Analysis: Ten individuals per species were chosen for Measurement based on the Rule of 10 (Gotelli & Ellison, 2004), following convenience from students involved in the Project. I conducted some basic descriptive tests and a single classification ANOVA following Sokal & Rohlf (1981). ANOVA was calculated using a Microsoft Excel Macro, as a complementary analysis. All other procedures and data management were conducted in Excel.

Studied Species: Species were chosen on the basis of commonness across the City, the country area (South US) and some of them are distributed worldwide, since we needed to avoid the lack of taxonomic expertise on students. Measurements have been taken on a number of species but we chose the following species to be included in the paper based on data quality: Gumbo Limbo, Flamboyant, Mango, Avocado and Yellow Trumpet Tree.

Gumbo Limbo (Edward & Watson, 2015).

Its scientific name is *Bursera simaruba*. This tree is a fast-growing tree that has a bark with a reddish tint that peels away, revealing a smooth under bark layer. This tree successfully blooms around winter, and prospers with little to no care. This tree belongs to the family Burseraceae, and is said to have originated native to North America. The Gumbo Limbo is tolerant to droughts, strong winds, and neglect.

Figure 3.-

Gumbo limbo. Detail of the remarkable bark that when mature is always peeling off. Photo by the Author.

Flamboyant (UF/IFAS. 2017). Native to Madagascar, royal poinciana trees are known for their showy flowers. The botanical name is derived from the Greek words *delos* (meaning conspicuous) and *onyx* (meaning claw), referring to their appearance. With four spoon-shaped petals about 3 inches long, and one slightly larger petal (called the standard), they resemble orchids, and range in color from deep red to bright orange. Yellow-flowering cultivars also exist.

These lovely flowers first appear in clusters between May and July, and can stay on the tree for a month or more.

The *Delonix regia*, or commonly known as the Flamboyant, Flame Tree, and Royal Poinciana, is a tree of tremendous beauty (Tropicos). During its bloom in the season of summer, it grows large and bright red flowers that usually cover most of the tree branches but younger specimens have less of the red foliage. *Delonix regia* can be found in many places, though native to Madagascar it has been transported to many tropical and subtropical regions, namely the Caribbean, Central and South America, tropical and subtropical regions of the US. It has also been introduced to other areas like the Indian subcontinent and South Africa.

Figure 4.-

Common name Flamboyant or Poinciana. Orange flowers and dark brown sheathed-pods. Photo by the Author.

Mango (Tropicos.org. Missouri Botanical Garden, 2018, Randy's Tropical Plants, Nd). *Mangifera indica*, the Mango has been cultivated for over four thousand years and by some accounts for over six thousand years. Originally from northern India, the mango has spread to every tropical corner of the world. Easily the most consumed fruit in the world, with worldwide production at around 35 million tons produced annually. The mango is an evergreen tree with alternate simple leaves that are 6-14" in length and 2-4" wide. Many different cultivars exist, so the fruit is greatly variable in size shape and color. The fruit contains a single large seed which is not easily removed from the pulp. Now, mangos are cultivated in many countries of Southeast Asia. It is said that the introduction to of mangos to Africa and South America occurred in the

sixteenth century. Mexico acquired the mango in the nineteenth century, and it entered Florida in 1833. The cultivated mango varieties are the result of constant selection by man from original wild plants for over 4,000 years.

Avocado (Crane, J.H., C.F. Balerdi & I. Maguire, 2016). A medium (30 ft; 9.1 m) to large (65 ft; 19.8 m) tree, the avocado tree is classified as an evergreen, although some varieties lose their leaves for a short time before and during flowering. The fruit is a berry, consisting of a single large seed, surrounded by a buttery pulp. Florida avocado varieties contain 3 to 15% oil. The skin is variable in thickness and texture. Fruit color at maturity may be green, black, purple or reddish, depending on variety. Fruit shape ranges from spherical to pyriform, and the fruit weigh from a few ounces to 5 lbs (2.3 kg).

Avocado varieties are classified in three groups, known as the West Indian, Guatemalan and Mexican "races". West Indian avocados originated in the tropical lowland areas of southern Mexico and Central America whereas the Guatemalan and Mexican avocados originated in mid-altitude highlands in Guatemala and Mexico.

Yellow Trumpet Tree (UF/IFAS, 2017). *Handroanthus chrysotrichus*, previously known by the scientific name *Tabebuia chrysotricha*, golden trumpet tree is native to Central American and northern South America. In addition to the golden trumpet, there are several other trumpet trees with various flower colors, including pink and purple, that share most of its desirable traits and should also be considered for wider use. The tree can be up to 80 feet tall in its native habitat, but usually reaches 30–40 feet in cultivation, making it a good size for most home landscapes. The open, spreading canopy makes it an attractive shade tree for Florida's hot summers. Golden trumpet tree grows well in Florida's sandy soils and is drought tolerant, though it needs regular water for the first several weeks after planting. It will perform best in sunny locations. Trees can be started from seed -just wait for the seed pods to crack open and then plant them in a light, moist potting medium- and then transplanted into the landscape once they are large enough.

Figure 5.-
Yellow Trumpet Tree bloom. Photo by the Author.

Results & Discussion

Aboveground Biomass.

Aboveground biomass calculated on the studied species is included in Table 1. Biomass ranged from 7.28 kg in Yellow Trumpet trees to 18826.51 kg in Mango trees. Differences observed among species were not significant ($F= 2.52, p > 0.05$).

Table 1.-
Measurements taken on trees and basic statistics. Measurements are expressed in Kg.

Species/ Individuals	Biomass Gumbo	Biomass Mango	Biomass Avocado	Biomass Flamboyant	Biomass Yellow Trumpet
1	120.44	300.14	6244.12	4083.83	506.18
2	183.71	580.66	1755.84	82.90	9.88
3	140.07	464.95	2789.47	52.73	7.28
4	98.16	18826.51	3524.23	642.90	37.41
5	168.86	9144.21	1250.24	788.72	160.47
6	136.30	349.01	3788.24	277.05	20.17
7	151.71	257.46	1810.98	524.49	68.50

Species/ Individuals	Biomass Gumbo	Biomass Mango	Biomass Avocado	Biomass Flamboyant	Biomass Yellow Trumpet
8	114.60	618.41	2140.65	1458.63	11.55
9	82.89	179.37	1757.28	1586.60	17.99
10	60.67	1073.08	2347.37	2102.04	29.97
Average	125.74	3179.38	2740.84	1159.99	86.94
Maximun	183.71	18826.51	6244.12	4083.83	506.18
Minimum	60.67	179.37	1250.24	52.73	7.28

The graph of the tree biomass calculated in the selected species is presented below data collected in the framework of the projects carried out exhibiting higher quality are presented (Fig. 6).

We recommend the use of models where tree biomass is determined from DBH only, which has a practical advantage over methods using height as well, because most of the inventories include DBH measurements. Moreover, the DBH is easy to measure accurately in the field. Although models that incorporate Height usually give good-fits (Brown *et al.* 1989, Brown 1997, Overman *et al.* 1994, Araujo *et al.* 1999, Schroeder *et al.* 1997), however, in many cases these models are not practical because the measurements of these variables are difficult to carry out with high accuracy, particularly in closed forests.

Figure 6.-

Graph of the biomass in 10 trees of five of the species studied, Mango, Gumbo Limbo, Avocado, Flamboyant, and Yellow Trumpet Tree.

Carbon Stock (CO).

As for Carbon Dioxide stocks (Table 2, Fig. 7), highly significant differences were found to exist among species ($F= 3.39$, $p < 0.01$). Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) is the GHG with the greatest impact on climate change. Global CO₂ emissions increased at an annual rate of 2.6% between 1960 and 2011, almost quadrupling from 9.4 billion tons to 34 billion tons. This strong increase is mainly due to the increase in the use of fossil fuels and also, although to a lesser extent, to the changes in the use of land represented by, for example, deforestation.

As explained in the IPCC Report on land use (IPCC, 2000), carbon is exchanged naturally between terrestrial ecosystems and the atmosphere through the processes of photosynthesis, respiration, decomposition and combustion. This situation is altered when, by human activity, a change is made in the use of land through, for example, forest logging. Conversely, newly planted or regenerating forests can absorb carbon for 20 to 50 years or even longer, depending on the species and conditions of the site. Carbon is absorbed by both vegetation and soils. The forests with the highest carbon storage in the world are boreal and tropical (Herreros *et al.* 2012).

Table 2.-

CO calculated on trees and basic statistics. Measurements are expressed in Kg.

Species/ Individuals	Carbon Stock Gumbo	Carbon Stock Mango	Carbon Stock Avocado	Carbon Stock Flamboyant	Carbon Stock Yellow Trumpet
1	60.22	150.07	3122.06	2041.91	253.09
2	91.86	290.33	877.92	41.45	4.94
3	70.03	232.48	1394.73	26.37	3.64
4	49.08	9413.25	1762.11	321.45	18.70
5	84.43	4572.10	625.12	394.36	80.23
6	68.15	174.50	1894.12	138.53	10.09
7	75.85	128.73	905.49	262.24	34.25
8	57.30	309.21	1070.32	729.31	5.77
9	41.45	89.69	878.64	793.30	9.00
10	60.67	6605.25	1173.69	1051.02	14.98
Average	65.90	2196.56	1370.42	579.99	43.47
Maximun	91.86	9413.25	3122.06	2041.91	253.09
Minimun	41.45	89.69	625.12	26.37	3.64

Figure 7.-

Graph of the Carbon Stock in 10 trees of the five species studied, Mango, Gumbo limbo, Avocado, Flamboyant, and Yellow Trumpet Tree.

This is the main reason why we find so important to conduct a Project like this with the participation of College students. It certainly creates awareness on issues like climate change, deforestation, and the importance of trees in urban spaces, among others. Another related topic that we bring up into this context is PES. The concept of Payment for Ecosystem Services (PES) has recently emerged as a promising tool for enhancing or safeguarding the provision of ecosystem services (ES) (*vid. v.d. Sand, 2012*).

PES establishes an incentive mechanism through which ES beneficiaries pay ES providers for the provision of these services. Although the concept has been extensively scrutinized in terms of its potential positive and negative impacts on the poor (e.g., Suyanto *et al.* 2007, Bulte *et al.* 2008), less attention has been paid to examining the role of PES in the context of adaptation to climate change.

Literature on PES typically distinguishes between four different kinds of services for which payments are made: hydrological or watershed services, carbon sequestration, biodiversity protection, and landscape beauty (e.g., Landell-Mills & Porras 2002, Wunder 2005). There are two ways of looking at Carbon sequestration, one is from the ecosystem perspective quantify the biomass of ecosystem areas using indirect measures, and then through it calculate the amount of

CO stored, or, measuring CO stored on individual trees from a significant sample and then extrapolate up to the ecosystem.

Conclusions

This project constitutes a simple approach and assessment of the outcome of Photosynthesis: the creation of Biomass. The importance of Photosynthesis is crucial to humans since it produces the oxygen that we breathe and the food that we eat, directly and indirectly, its implications in the current context of climate change due to the CO₂ that is sequestered through the process are of paramount importance. The Project's simplicity makes it easy to replicate since it involves measuring Perimeters on common tree species in urban areas, using a Tailor's tape for making the measurements, and finally conducting analyses using an Excel spreadsheet with formulas already programmed for Students to input data get results. The possibility of this Biology course Project being adopted by other Professors and Teachers would contribute data on Biomass and CO₂ stored on common tree species across the country, which would be a major contribution to the study of climate change on urban areas with the inclusion of College, University and High School Students.

Acknowledgements

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Data for conducting these analyses were compiled from student original Projects by Vanessa Jaramillo (BSC 1005 Student from the Fall Course of 2016).

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Conclusions

This project constitutes a simple approach and assessment of the outcome of Photosynthesis: the creation of Biomass. The importance of Photosynthesis is crucial to humans since it produces the oxygen that we breathe and the food that we eat, directly and indirectly, its implications in the current context of climate change due to the CO₂ that is sequestered through the process are of paramount importance. The Project's simplicity makes it easy to replicate since it involves measuring Perimeters on common tree species in urban areas, using a Tailor's tape for making the measurements, and finally conducting analyses using an Excel spreadsheet with formulas already programmed for Students to input data get results. The possibility of this Biology course Project being adopted by other Professors and Teachers would contribute data on Biomass and CO₂ stored on common tree species across the country, which would be a major contribution to the study of climate change on urban areas with the inclusion of College, University and High School Students.

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